

Kinetic Typography in Digital Media

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Abstract

Kinetic typography, which involves the dynamic presentation of text through motion graphics, has become increasingly prevalent in digital media. While gaining immense popularity, the in-depth study on the current state of kinetic typography in digital media still stands a gap. This study therefore seeks to bridge this gap through a systematic review of secondary research data on kinetic typography. Issues investigated in the review are the design principles, including font, colour, motion, and sound, that influence the efficiency of kinetic typography in digital media. The study asserts that issues surrounding context, purpose, and audience in the design of kinetic typography form the basis of consideration in this area, and further research is encouraged to appreciate its potential effects on user experiences. The current review serves the purpose of presenting a current state of knowledge on kinetic typography in digital media to serve as a base for future research and practical implementation in the field.

Keywords: *Kinetic Typography, Typography, Graphic Design, Motion graphics, Digital Media.*

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Introduction

Due to its capacity to grab viewers' attention and deliver messages in an interesting and memorable fashion, the use of kinetic typography has grown in popularity in digital media. Kinetic typography combines animated text with motion graphics, sound, and other elements to produce a dynamic visual experience that may be utilised for a range of projects, such as social media posts, instructional videos, and advertising. The effectiveness of kinetic typography in digital media is not well studied, despite its rising popularity. There is a need for research that particularly evaluates the usage of kinetic typography in digital media and its impact on user engagement and comprehension. Prior studies have concentrated on the design principles of kinetic typography generally. This study will add to the body of knowledge already available and offer a more thorough understanding of the application of kinetic typography in digital media.

Review of Literature

The study "Kinetic Typography -Figuration and Technology (2020)" by Nikolina Stanic Loknar describes in detail how modern new media permits changing of the format, size, assignment, and movement and diversifies the typical typographic notions into kinetic typography. It provides a detailed exploration of how sequel movie titles can use kinetic typography and how this affects the audience's perspective.

Bertrand and Mogual (2021) – “Why do we need the words to dance?” - provides a thorough examination of the expressive and creative potential of dynamic typography. It goes over the different methods and design tenets needed to produce captivating and lively text animations.

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Hye-Junk Lee & Soyoung Park (2023) – “What drives the learning benefits of moving text? A theoretical discussion for learning implications of kinetic typography” - offers in-depth understanding and insights on the appropriate use of typography as motion to communicate ideas. The article explores how moving text can improve understanding and retention by delving into the theoretical basis and learning implications of kinetic typography. It presents a compelling argument for the usage of kinetic typography in learning contexts by highlighting its advantages for the brain and its possible educational uses.

Methodology

- By doing secondary research and comparing the efficiency of kinetic typography principles in digital media.
- Collecting commercials, music videos, and websites that uses kinetic typography.
- Examining how digital media targets the user using typeface, color, motion, and sound based on the data collected.

Data Collection and Analysis

Collected necessary commercials, music videos, voiceovers, and brand logos that use kinetic typography, then compared how well those principles work in digital media. based on the obtained data, examined how digital media addresses the user utilising typeface, colour, motion, and sound. to comprehend how kinetic typography can be used to evoke emotions in viewers, which can have a significant impact on engagement and comprehension. To comprehend how the audience can remember the information presented in the kinetic typography after the message has been delivered, how it makes the audience remember that even after the time has passed.

Secondary research acts as the source of the data for this study. The sources of the data for this study included typography-related books, research papers, and websites.

Results and Discussion

Figure 1. Brand Logo
Source: Nike's SNKRS app

With only one logo, it encapsulates all of the company's ideals. Nike's logo initially shows as normal, followed by a basketball player, Converse, then SNKRS. After seeing the logo, the designer provides a thorough explanation of what users might expect from the app.

The New York Times: Turkish Edition

Figure 2. Commercial “Launch of Turkish Edition of the New York Times”

Source: Official YouTube Channel “Quba Michalski”

The New York Times is built on words, so it’s poetic that this video builds recognizable landmarks from newspaper pages. The financial news pages were used for Wall Street and the entertainment news became Times Square. As this video is all about bringing the American newspaper to Turkey, the video takes viewers on a tour from Manhattan to Istanbul, all with the wonder of typography.

Honda - Keep Up

Figure 3. Commercial “Keep Up – Honda”

Source: Official YouTube Channel “Honda”

The unusual "Italian," reversed-contrast typeface was created to purposefully capture readers' attention by contradicting their expectations. At first, we looked at the high-contrast Didone typefaces, which are regarded by many as some of the most beautiful typefaces currently in use. No other typographic design has ever elicited as many unfavorable responses as the Italian. The product of this effort, Karloff, ties the monstrous Italians to the high contrast Modern style of Bodoni and Didot. A single design element, the contrast between the thick and the thin, determines whether a form is attractive or repellent.

Discussion

Digital media research on kinetic typography has given important light on how well this technique works to improve user interaction and communication. In studies on kinetic typography, the following main conclusions were drawn:

- Information retention is increased by kinetic typography in digital media, according to research. According to studies, moving text is more interesting and memorable than static text, which improves comprehension and information retention.
- Impact on the emotions of the viewer: Kinetic typography is a powerful tool for establishing emotional connections with the audience. According to studies, the combination of motion and color in kinetic typography can evoke strong emotions including excitement, surprise, and amazement.
- Kinetic typography is an effective method for engaging consumers in digital media because it can draw in and hold their attention. According to studies, animated text can improve user experiences by grabbing the viewer's interest and keeping it there.

Conclusion

Research on the effects of various design aspects, such as motion, color, and font, on the viewing experience could be the main topic of kinetic typography in digital media. To learn more about how these design aspects affect user engagement, comprehension, and emotional response, this could involve user testing and surveys.

There is a significant need for more accessible digital media, and study on kinetic typography might examine how this method can be utilized to increase accessibility for those with disabilities. The use of kinetic typography in conjunction with other accessibility tools, such as screen readers and captioning, may be one such area of research.

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